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Policy Brief No. 8

Different Realities After Cancer: Why Personalised Support Matters for Quality of Life

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Cancer and its treatments often leave lasting impacts on individual's physical, emotional, and social wellbeing. While overall survival rates have improved, many individuals report ongoing challenges that affect daily life long after diagnosis and treatment. This study aimed to better understand how quality of life varies among people living with and beyond cancer by identifying distinct patterns of experiences and needs. Using a data-driven approach, we explored how health-related quality of life clusters into groups and examined factors associated with these patterns, to inform more personalised healthcare and support strategies.

Research Findings

This study identified three distinct health-related quality of life (HRQoL) profiles among those living with and beyond cancer using a person-centred latent profile analysis approach. These profiles; high wellbeing, compromised wellbeing, and low wellbeing; highlight substantial differences in individual experiences that is not captured by average HRQoL scores alone. Physical strength was linked with better quality of life, while more nutrition related symptoms and working were associated with poorer outcomes. Participants generally reported more symptoms and lower functioning than the general population, highlighting the ongoing challenges faced by those affected by cancer.

Policy Implications

Our study suggests that HRQoL interventions should not be one-size-fits-all but rather tailored to the needs of each individual. The identification of distinct HRQoL profiles, such as those seen in this study, presents an opportunity to personalise care strategies and enhance the effectiveness of interventions. For example, those in the low QoL group may benefit from more intensive physical rehabilitation and psychosocial support, whereas those in the high QoL group may require less frequent follow-up and interventions. Implementing personalised care plans, along with routine screening for symptoms of physical deconditioning, nutrition issues, and mental health concerns, can improve the overall experience and help individuals achieve a higher quality of life post-treatment.

Industry Recommendations

Healthcare providers, digital health companies, and insurers can play key roles in improving survivorship care. Industry should invest in tools and services that assess and monitor patients' quality of life in real time, integrate strength and nutrition measures into care platforms, and support personalised intervention pathways. Employers and occupational health programmes should recognise the ongoing impacts of cancer on work ability and wellbeing and offer flexible support for survivors. Developers of patient-reported outcome measures, wearable technologies, and tele-health platforms can further enhance personalised care by helping clinicians track and respond to individual needs throughout recovery and beyond.

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Further Reading:
Keaver, R. and McLaughlin, C.
(2025) Understanding the Diverse
Experiences of Those Living with
and Beyond Cancer: Implications
for Personalised Care from a
Latent Profile Analysis of HRQoL.
Cancers, 17(10), 1698
DOI: [10.3390/cancers17101698](https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers17101698)

**National Smart Specialisation
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